

Deliverable 9.2 Educational Curriculum Design Guidelines

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Executive Summary

This Report is part of Task 9.2 in Work Package 9 and based on the findings of the DIAMOND Project. There is a current worldwide recognition that the current transport systems inadequately address gendered differences in terms of the current infrastructure and the delivery of services, and that gender equity has not been realized.

The findings from DIAMOND suggests that women as users of transport services for example are often concerned with availability, accessibility, safety, awareness, and cost. In relation to employability, women are concerned with their career development and flexible working opportunities.

To address these concerns, the DIAMOND project has developed curriculum design guidelines to provide a roadmap for adaptation of training and studies content in relation to new skills and opportunities in the transport system. The Guidelines will be distributed among the European training and educational centres.

The main aim is to develop a new level of curriculum design guidelines for educational institutions and future transport professionals to deliver excellence in education and ensure equity in the transport sector. Essential to achieving the above stated objective is to design novel educational content to address the following items:

- ◆ How technologies should adapt to women needs
- ◆ How to match job opportunities with women motivations, talents and needs
- ◆ How to design job characteristics and disseminate to attract women
- ◆ How to carry out HR processes to avoid bias and discrimination, and cover psychology aspects in the different stages of employment including getting into education, workforce, job recruitment, retention, progression in jobs, etc.
- ◆ Future skills needed for job positions
- ◆ How to design transport services to meet women's requirements and expectations, and improve their access to transport and jobs

The Guidelines are targeted at EU Universities and training centres offering graduate and postgraduate studies, in-company and occupational training on Transport Technologies and Management. They show how to handle gender needs in transport planning, in service offerings, and how to tackle job opportunities in a fair way is generated based on the project outputs, in relation to:

- ◆ new skills identified in transport related job
- ◆ new jobs and services opportunities
- ◆ women attitudes and talent towards new technologies, business models
- ◆ impact of women in Technology (adaptation of new technologies related to transport and women's needs)

The expected outcome of the guidelines will be an increased readiness of transport systems and educational courses for gender inclusion based on a better understanding of women talents and motivations in job opportunities.

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Terminology and Acronyms

CEDAW	<i>Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women</i>
CSW	<i>Commission on the Status of Women</i>
ECOSOC	<i>Economic and Social Council</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
EUT	<i>FUNDACIO EURECAT</i>
HEI	<i>Higher Education Institutions</i>
HR	<i>Human Resources</i>
IT	<i>Information Technology</i>
ICT	<i>Information Communications Technology</i>
UC-I	<i>Use Case I</i>
UC-II	<i>Use Case II</i>
UC-III	<i>Use Case III</i>
UC-IV	<i>Use Case IV</i>

I Introduction

I.1 Overview

The principle of gender equality has been established by the Commission on the Status of Women (CSW) and the United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC). The CSW is concerned with promoting gender equality to Eliminate of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) (United Nations, 1996). CEDAW underscores the role of education in promoting the equality of men and women, it also enjoins parties to take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women to ensure to their equal rights with men (AQU Catalunya, 2019).

Similarly, the Treaty on European Union (TEU, 2010) establishes the principle of equality between women and men as a common value within the EU (Art. 2), according to the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (Art. 23, 2000), the equality of women and men is also a fundamental right that must be guaranteed in all spheres of activity. These agreements fight against any form of discrimination based on sex and legitimise the introduction of measures to eradicate any form of inequality between women and men (TEU Art. 141.4)

The DIAMOND Project has commissioned this Educational Curriculum Design Guidelines to support EU Universities and training centres offering graduate, postgraduate studies and in-company and occupational training to think creatively about how to design educational courses for gender inclusion based on a better understanding of women mobility needs, talent and motivations to address the discrimination in the transport sector.

The basic principle that should guide educators and Higher Education Institutions (HEI) is fairness and equity, the design should respond to the barriers and other forms of biases within the transport system affecting equity and female employability in different areas in the transport sector and transport accessibility. In essence there should be a shift in focus on how job characteristics is designed, and how should they be disseminated to attract women, how HR processes are carried out to avoid bias and discrimination, and cover aspects in the different stages of employment such as job recruitment, retention, progression in jobs and, how transport services are designed to meet women's requirements and expectations, and improve their access to transport and to jobs. The responsibility should be on institutions to change and adapt their policies and practice to meet women's requirements and expectations, and improve access to jobs in the transport sector, retention, progression in jobs and, access to transport.

The aim of this report is to provide a new level of curriculum design guidelines for future transport professionals. The guide provides practical support within a framework of principles of curriculum design and guidelines. It is designed to help programme leaders identify relevant issues in the transport sector to discuss with their teams. The educational novel contents are designed to address the following items:

- ◆ How technologies should adapt to women needs
- ◆ How to match job opportunities with women motivations, talents and needs
- ◆ How to design job characteristics and disseminate to attract women
- ◆ How to carry out HR processes to avoid bias and discrimination, and cover psychology aspects in the different stages of employment including getting into education, workforce, job recruitment, retention, progression in jobs, etc.
- ◆ Future skills needed for job positions
- ◆ How to design transport services to meet women's requirements and expectations, and improve their access to transport and jobs

The Guidelines provides a guide on topics of particular relevance to learning and teaching across EU Universities and training centres offering graduate and postgraduate studies, in-company and occupational training on how to handle gender needs in transport planning, service provision, and how to fairly design and disseminate job opportunities.

The expected outcome of the guidelines will be an increased readiness of transport systems and educational courses for gender inclusion based on a better understanding of women needs, talents and motivations in job opportunities.

1.2 Definition of women

The DIAMOND project has adopted a broad working definition of women for this project which is underpinned by the acknowledgement that gender (as opposed to only the biological sex class definition of women) is a social construction which changes over time and space (DIAMOND Project 2020; Guenther, Humbert and Kelan 2018). From this perspective gender is understood as the specific cultural meaning attached to the roles of men and women across and within societies. In the main gender looks to explain, in a rigid societal framework, the social norms, attitudes, and activities that each culture deems appropriate for one sex over the other at a specific moment in time (Koester, 2015). Gender ideology therefore contains an innate power structure with reference to the public and private lives and experiences of women and girls' which impact on their role in the workplace, the academy, sports, and the arts (Scott 2018). The power imbalance associated with societal gendered roles has led Koester (2015) to described gender as the “most persistent cause, consequence and manifestation of power relations” (ibid 2015:1) globally. By providing a gendered distinction between men and women, Koester argues we are also identifying and labelling power and powerlessness. Therefore, when we explore the barriers and facilitators faced by women employed in and using public transport, we must also acknowledge the wider societal inequalities associated with their gender identity. Employing a gender focus in the project opposed to biological sex class also allows us to collect data from biological women and those who self-identify as women and live their life as a woman. Recognising that there are different legal and other definitions and recognitions across the EU and elsewhere, the general definition of women adopted by the DIAMOND project is based on the broad concept of gender as a social construction which changes over time and space and allows us to examine the varying experiences of women.

1.3 Definition of Fairness

Women generally, and different groups of women specifically, can have complex mobility patterns in comparison to men e.g., mothers and older women report taking shorter commuting times but more journeys than men (McQuaid and Chen 2012; Madariaga 2013; Houston and Tilley 2016; Hanson 2010). It is also claimed that current transport systems do not always take these gendered differences into account when either planning or delivering services. Additionally, for many women driving private vehicles modelled on the general physicality of men has also created issues with regards to seating, posture and the seatbelt safety; while self-driving cars may use algorithms based on databases which reflect past biases in car use rather than fairness across the potential population of users (for a full view of discussion see Deliverable 2.2 of DIAMOND).

Fairness can be a vague and somewhat ambiguous concept which can evolve and change over time and space and can be based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences. This makes any attempt at producing a universal definition a difficult process. The terms “fairness” and “justice” tend to be used to describe both how decisions are made and how individuals are treated within a community. Throughout the wider literature the notion of fairness is closely related to the concepts of **justice, equity and human rights**. Hence fairness needs to reflect access or opportunity to use the transport system, but also the distribution of benefits across the transport system.

A key issue relevant to the broader definition of “fairness” relates to equality and there are two ways in which equality impacts on fairness in relation to transport: equality of opportunities and equality of outcomes (Hail and McQuaid 2021). Both are sometimes intertwined, but for this deliverable we will separate them. In the context of the fairness for women as transport users, equality of opportunity can be seen to relate to such issues as accessibility to suitable transport services. Equality of opportunity can therefore be defined as a state of fairness in which all groups of people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices, unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except when they can be explicitly justified for example cheaper fares for young or low-income people (see for instance, Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy). In other words, equality of opportunity should provide fair and equal opportunities for people with a variety of different characteristics to access a safe, secure, effective, and efficient transport systems that meets their daily needs.

Even if such formal equality of opportunity (and lack of formal discrimination) between groups exists, there may be a need for substantive equality of outcomes where indirect discrimination may exist. For instance, those who have primary responsibilities for young children when travelling should have full access to services (e.g., when using pushchairs). This ‘fair access’ should be the case irrespective of the sex of the person responsible for the child, but in most cases, this would be a woman. Hence this particular barrier mainly, (but not solely) affects women and under the umbrella of equality of opportunity, a ‘fair’ transport system would seek to remove the barrier. In contrast to equality of opportunity, the equality of outcome approach “focuses attention on the outcomes or end results of policies and programmes, imposing an expectation that an absence of inequity of any sort would be a hall-mark of a fair system” (Bowling 2007:23).

For both Litman (2018) and Gullo et al. (2008) fairness in relation to transport mainly relates to equality of opportunity as without adequate transport, access to education or employment is difficult, which further impacts income equality. Litman (2018) separates the concept of

equity into two separate types, horizontal which relates to the egalitarian concept of equal treatment of equals and vertical equity which is related to social justice and social inclusion and focuses on the difference (in ability or need) between and within groups, i.e., transport policies which favour disadvantaged groups such as people with disabilities.

Lee, Sener and Jones (2017) introduce five separate types of equity, which they argue are related specifically to fairness with regards to public use of and access to public transport.

- **Social equity** – analysis of social groups and is measured using variables based on income, race, sex and age etc.
- **Spatial equity** – is a geographical level of analysis which looks to examine where the inequality is taking place, this is important in relation to transport policy planning “because the effects of public policies tend to cluster around specific physical locations” (p. 213)
- **Procedural equity** – is associated with equity in the policy making process as opposed to the outcome of policy, in the case of transport policy planning procedural equity is related to having fair and equal evaluations included in the policy making decision.
- **Modal equity** – is related to ensuring that there is safe access for all groups to the range of local transport modes, the example provided is that “because walking and bicycling have higher mortality rates from vehicle accidents than driving, modal equity strategies would seek to restrict driving in order to slow or reduce vehicle traffic” (p. 215)
- **Distribution equity** – is linked to how transportation costs and benefits are distributed across society, currently this is evaluated for fairness by examining the accessibility to transport infrastructures which excludes any evaluation of how safely and easily people can travel to the station.

Pereira, Schwanen and Banister (2017) use the theoretical frameworks of Rawls’ egalitarianism and Sen’s Capability Approaches to argue that distributive justice concerns over transport disadvantage and social exclusion should focus primarily on accessibility as a human capability. This suggests that transport policies should explicitly consider their *distributional effects* and also set minimum standards of *accessibility* to key destinations. Policies should also prioritise disadvantaged groups, reduce inequalities of opportunities and mitigate transport externalities, while respecting individuals’ rights. They argue that a fair distribution of accessibility should include “firstly, that individuals’ basic rights and liberties should never be violated or sacrificed on the grounds of improving the accessibility levels of others. Secondly, a transport policy is fair if it distributes transport investments and services in ways that reduce inequality of opportunity. While aiming to enhance overall levels of accessibility, policies should prioritise vulnerable groups and thereby mitigate morally arbitrary disadvantages that systematically reduce their accessibility levels, such as being elderly, disabled, or born in an ethnic minority or poor family” (p. 184). This approach supports the setting of minimum standards of accessibility to key destinations, guaranteed by governmental social or transport policies. Lucas, van Wee and Maat (2015) further argue that fairness in transport involves access to opportunities to participate in activities, that an individual values, at a minimum level (such as health, employment, and education).

For a fair exchange the benefits must come back, in some way, to the users and potential users of transport (distributional issues). For example, an equitable exchange between the government (giving subsidies) and rail companies must also take into account train passengers *and* those suffering externalities (like noise or air pollution) *and* non-users (who may be put off travelling due to timetables or costs etc.). Fairness also must be accompanied by good governance, high levels of accountability and of transparency to all interested groups. This means taking account of the social costs and benefits, as well as financial ones, of poor transport (Social Exclusion Unit 2003).

A working **definition of fairness** for the DIAMOND project is: a state in which people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices or unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except they can be explicitly justified

The themes identified in this deliverable are to support the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the project surveys (including focus groups/ interviews). The themes highlight measures of unfairness that reflect revealed unfairness through actual behaviour (e.g., time travel to work, as a longer time may reflect fewer job opportunities in general); or perceptions (e.g., security fears, although these may or may not reflect actual risks); or direct perceptions (e.g., feelings of discrimination). Based on the Grant Agreement, previous WPs, and the literature review below, three main fairness themes related to transport systems which are inclusive of all demographic factors such as age, disability and ethnicity are identified as listed below:

Capable of meeting required needs of people (in relation to people’s job roles, flexible working, training etc. ability to travel in an appropriately designed transport system, meeting basic expectations and being environmentally sound)

Accessible (ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value; accessible to all groups also in terms of design and comfort provided, e.g., those with children, and in terms of fares and costs for those with lower income, including distribution of costs and benefits; all people can fairly access jobs for which they are suitable)

Safe and Secure (ability to travel or work safely and securely for all type of users)

Under each Use Case factors are identified that are particularly important, or where there are significant gaps in research.

From the above perspective, inequitable or unfair transport policies and planning can have diverse and significant impacts on various groups at various times in relation to individuals’ economic and social opportunities (see D2.2 for a DIAMOND definition of fairness). Although the focus of this project is fair access for women, ‘fairness’ applies to all people, but certain types of unfairness disproportionately affect people with certain characteristics, in particular, women (or groups such as women with young children).

To fill this knowledge gap and further the understanding and need for gender and diversity in the transport sector, the Diamond project has developed curriculum design guidelines to provide a roadmap for adaptation of training and studies content in relation to new skills and opportunities in the transport system. The main aim is to develop a new level of curriculum design guidelines for educational institutions and future transport professionals to deliver excellence in education and close the gender gap in the transport sector.

The educational guideline is to provide measures and recommendations, to ensure equity in the transport sector. The trainee will be introduced to a range of methods and best practices and given guides on how to achieve equity in different aspect in the transport sector.

2. Women needs in the transport sector

In our increasingly more fluid world, issues relating to women mobility and employment in the transport sector are essential due the disparities between men and women in the sector. Women mobility and employment in the transport sector are at the core of various studies due their influence on many social, financial, and environmental dimensions. Women mobility and employment in the transport sector remains relevant. To understand the issues and complexity of women mobility and to confront it through transport planning, the education of future transport professional on the key issues confronting women in the transport sector is potentially useful. The limited amount of time and resources of universities and training institutions to train future professionals poses a problem: where should the teaching priorities be? The Diamond project has investigated this subject by asking a number of gender experts, users of the transport systems and employee in the transport sector and presented the needs and challenges according to their personal viewpoint for curriculum considerations.

2.1 Women needs as users of the transport system (UC-I, UC-II and UC-III)

The literature on women and access to public transport highlights the specific issues faced by women including accessibility whilst traveling with childcare responsibilities which constrain their travel options. McQuaid and Chen (2012) discuss the complex travel patterns of women and mothers specifically, who tend to make more and shorter journeys. Lucas et al. (2019) argue that access to suitable mobility options should be accepted as part of all of our human rights, but claims that at times these rights can be compromised particularly “for women who face physical, economic, cultural and psychological” inequalities in relation to their participation in social life and access to public transport and suggest that fair access for disabled and elderly (women) in public transport is impacted specifically by “infrequent and irregular services” which compounds their experiences of unequal access to social life and in particular health care.

Transport accessibility includes: the availability of and physical access to the transport system (e.g. stations and other facilities and vehicles etc; service levels of the system (e.g. cost of travel, comfort, travel time); the spatial distribution of activities, including the location of services and facilities people are seeking access to (e.g. availability of bike sharing points in low income but low use areas); and cultural diversity (especially in a low income country context) (Geurs et al., 2009, pp.76-7).

The existing literature also shows us that in the main, the wider travel behaviour of men and women varies significantly with women, especially those with childcare responsibilities, tending to travel less for work than men do and make multiple shorter and more complex journeys opposed to men who take longer and single journeys at different times of the day (Hanson 2010; Martens 2012; Levy 2013; Basaric et al. 2016). Louis and Hernandez (2016) claim, at an extremely aggregate level, that ordinarily “...men display standard and linear travel patterns

[and] women frequently have shorter travel patterns and more complex travel chains”. Further differences in travel patterns are attributed between different groups of men and women, with women who have children and women who do not have children. Analysing UK household surveys, McQuaid and Chen (2012) found variations between mothers and fathers with data showing that “fathers travel furthest to work while mothers travel least” (p. 66).

The DIAMOND Project used a data-driven approach to examine the level of accessibility of urban railway infrastructures by women users. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were used for the analysis of several geolocated open datasets related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland). See section 3, Deliverable 4.3 for full details; investigate women’s emotions as passengers of autonomous vehicles aimed at supporting the development of fully automated cars, able to dynamically adapt driving performance to women’s preferences; and to investigate women’s needs and barriers faced as users of bike sharing services using data mainly from France and the UK.

Responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception by transport users for fairness characteristics of the service in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features (see Chapter 6 of D4.3 for full details).

The Use-Case I investigates the accessibility of urban railway infrastructures by women users. A clear significant gender differences was observed with women having less access to transport, lower perception of and lower satisfaction with rail providers. In particular women seem to have greater concern and less satisfaction with safety and security issues. Results did indicate that issues around mobility, such as disability/chronic illness and caring responsibilities can have a large impact on users’ satisfaction with services. Similarly, it was note that different demographics and fairness characteristics were more meaningful in different countries, showing that consideration of contextual factors are essential.

The Use-Case II investigate women’s emotions as passengers of autonomous vehicles. The overall perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample was positive. Most of the results were consistent about the assessment of AV’s benefits with no differences by gender or by the presence of children in the family composition. In this context women indicated a higher sensitivity towards safety, greater need for accessibility and mobility with children in mind, and placing greater importance of energy efficiency.

Furthermore, women show greater interest in performing simultaneous activities than men, especially women with children under 12. For men and women with children interest in caring for other passengers is higher, but especially without children, keeping control of driving features is more important. Last but not least the willingness to purchase an AV differed pre-post experiment, women with children, before experiment were less willing to purchase an AV, however after the experiment they were much more including (when costs considerations were not taken into account).

The Use-Case III investigates the problem of bike-sharing. To promote and make bike-sharing systems sustainable, it has been found that overall user’s level of satisfaction was positively related to age, with younger respondents (18-44 years) being less critical of bike-sharing

systems than older respondents (45-74 years). Perception of safety was also a very relevant factor in bike sharing, and it was linked to traffic speed, and some infrastructural aspects such as the lack of cycling lanes. Similarly, visibility and adequate lighting at docking stations predicted increased sense of security and user satisfaction. Absence of accessories for transporting children and carting goods negatively impacted user satisfaction, with respondents indicating that provision would increase their level of satisfaction. Last but not least weather conditions had a significant impact on cycling and bike sharing; however, supply of cycling raincoats could help mitigate this and increase user satisfaction.

It was also pointed out that bike-sharing is highly attractive for potential tourists as part of a short urban holiday, as a frequent mode for multiple purposes. Therefore, cities that consider expanding their attraction as tourist destinations could benefit from bike-sharing schemes and bicycle infrastructure as an integral part of the touristic experience and could use the cycling experience as part as their branding strategy (Kaplan et al., 2015; Caulfield et al., 2017).

The following sections describe the use-cases and their respective key FCs (e.g., UCI: Public transport and infrastructure, UCII: autonomous vehicles, UCIII: Vehicle (bike) sharing).

Public transport infrastructures. Railways.

The objective of the Use-Case I is to investigate women's needs as users of metro and urban railway public transport and provide recommendations to improve the quality of the railway infrastructure, in particular of the railway stations and services from a gender perspective. Understanding the needs of women in terms of accessibility, comfort and safety within the stations but also in the entrances to the station. In particular, the main critical issues addressed are:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users):
 - ◆ Reliability and efficiency;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency for commuting;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency access to point of interest for all users;
 - ◆ Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc;
 - ◆ Wayfinding information;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency;
 - ◆ Service reliability;
 - ◆ Wayfinding information and integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Stations integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Design;
 - ◆ Directions in stations;
 - ◆ Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;
- b. ACCESSIBILITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Location of station;
 - ◆ Reliability and efficiency;
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users):

- ◆ Harassment and pickpocketing;
- ◆ Design of infrastructure and services;
- ◆ Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers;
- ◆ Overcrowding and emergency management.

The issues addressed in this relative use case are critical aspects of all transport systems (Cascetta, 2001; Meyer, 2016) They are more strongly focused on serving the needs of all users, the role of safety in the planning process, and transportation planning in the context of societal concerns, including the development of more sustainable transportation solutions.

More specifically and considering the Fairness Characteristics (FC) level 3 that has been used all over the project, the Top 10 most relevant FC after the Analytic Hierarchy process (AHP) and the Bayesian Network (BN) analysis for this Use-Case I (DIAMOND Project, 2021a) are:

1. Offering adequate personal space;
2. Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).
3. Improved ventilation and air-conditioning
4. Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points
5. Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.
6. Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety;
7. Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;
8. Number of service available within the transport infrastructure
9. Reliability of the service modes available
10. Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing

Autonomous Vehicles

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women's emotional needs as passengers of autonomous vehicles to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology and identify the key factors affecting women's travel choices for design consideration. The key findings are presented below:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (of drivers):
 - ◆ Multi-tasking;
 - ◆ Travel time;
 - ◆ Vehicle behaviour;
- b. ACCESSIBLE (for all drivers):
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (getting in and out of the car);
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (seating);
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (shopping/suitcases);
 - ◆ Human Machine Interface (ergonomics);
 - ◆ Human Machine Interface (warning and communication system);
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Trust in technology;

- ◆ Human Errors - Specific training for AV drivers;
- ◆ Safe ergonomics.

The way information is presented, as well as the correct timing of alerts are two crucial factors for the design of warning systems (Cao et al., 2009). A promising way to reduce transmission errors and to enhance system effectiveness is to present information using multiple modalities, e.g. visual, acoustic, or haptic driver feedback (Schwarz and Fastenmeier, 2017; Naujoks et al., 2019).

The Fairness Characteristics (FC) level 3 that has been used all over the project, the Top 10 most relevant FC after the AHP and the BN analysis for this Use-Case II (DIAMOND Project, 2021a) are:

1. Perception of boredom
2. Perception of joy
3. Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers
4. Perception of reduction of ecological impact
5. Importance on controlling speed
6. Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment
7. Trust in technology in the case of bad weather
8. Vehicle behaviour under sportive driving
9. Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour
10. Perception of public health when driving without steering wheel

Bike-sharing services

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate women's needs and barriers faced as users of bike sharing services in Europe and make recommendations to increase the use of bicycle sharing by women. The main issues raised to achieve the fairness include the following:

- a. **CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS** (for all users):
 - ◆ Suitable bikes for those traveling with children, carrying packages and shopping;
 - ◆ Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation in BAME communities;
 - ◆ Bikes suited to local topography and weather conditions;
 - ◆ Available to those in low-income neighbourhoods;
- b. **ACCESSIBILITY** (for all users):
 - ◆ Location of docking stations, proximity and convenience;
 - ◆ Costs including membership fees;
 - ◆ Service reliability;
 - ◆ Public awareness of scheme;
 - ◆ Simple and flexible signing-up process;
 - ◆ Payment option;
 - ◆ Sheltered docking stations;
- c. **SAFETY AND SECURITY** (for all users):
 - ◆ Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security;

- ◆ Separate biking infrastructure;
- ◆ Personal safety – maintenance of bikes;
- ◆ Safety equipment provided including helmets, hi-vis vest, ponchos;
- ◆ Ease of reporting problems/complaints about bike-sharing facilities

Issues relating to the capacity to meet required needs are closely related to other transport systems like aviation, logistic or maritime transport. Improving these aspects for the railway system has benefits for the other connected transport systems. Furthermore, the aspects relating to accessibility are closely related to urban design, considering the location of station, in terms of “the level of comfort and security of the transport infrastructures by walking” and “the public transport services nearby the transport infrastructures accessible with comfortable walking distance”. The improvement of these aspects implies a change from the point of view of urban architecture.

Specifically, the Fairness Characteristics (FC) level 3 that has been used all over the project, the Top 10 most relevant FC after the AHP and the BN analysis for this Use-Case III (DIAMOND Project, 2021a) are:

1. Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
2. Cycling rain Poncho
3. Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.
4. All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure
5. Attractive changing facilities
6. Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.
7. Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
8. Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities
9. Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
10. Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes

2.2 Women needs as employees in the Transport Sector

Literature on women’s employment in the transport sector is based on the historical concept of occupational and job segregation (Corral and Isusi 2007; French and Strachan 2008; Wright 2014; Giannelos et al. 2018; Yerkes et al., 2017) based on a gendered notion of employment which dictates which jobs are acceptable and suitable for men or women and Corral and Isusi (2007) adding that the transport sector is one of the most “gender segregated sectors of the economy” (p. 4). French and Strachan (2008) report that very few transport organisations use “proactive strategies” (p. 86) to recruit, promote and retain women employees, particularly amongst the management roles. The idea that many transport organisations still have this view of outdated gender stereotypes becomes visible in the ways that certain vacant roles are advertised all have an impact on the likelihood of women applying for roles, particularly at a management level.

There are still many (men and women) who believe that there are certain roles and careers that are more suited to men than women and vice versa. This gendered view of job roles has a direct impact on women in the workplace in relation to their working conditions which can also result in a lack of specific policies and facilities to support women in the workplace (Astor et al. 2017, Giannelos et al. 2018). Yerkes et al. (2017) highlight this by discussing the impact on women returning to work from maternity leave and the ways in which career breaks disadvantage women in their long terms career goals. The study reports that in some cases within the transport sector women are returning to work on a part time “lower occupational status” (p. 477) which they claim is unfair and creates issues around both procedural and interactional justice for working mothers. Similar impacts are observed in other sectors, including female dominated professions such as nursing (e.g., McIntosh et al. 2012). French and Strachan (2008) report that their research shows a positive correlation with providing robust maternity, pregnancy and breastfeeding policies with the retention of female employees. Adams et al. (2000) also claim that many organisations were still unsure of employing married women as they are generally regarded as having less commitment to their careers, although such attitudes are likely to have change since then.

In the investigation of women employment in the transport sector The DIAMOND Project in Use-Case IV found that job segregation has a significant impact on gender balance and female employability in the transport industry. Job segregation is based upon traditional or historical ideas of ‘men’s jobs and ‘women’s jobs. Despite gender imbalance in the industry, the dominance of male employees was apparent across sectors and locations. It was noted majority female are employment in HR, finance, marketing and clerical work, but less likely than men to be employed in front line jobs, such as driving, and engineering or IT jobs.

Moreover, while there was evidence of the lack of women in ‘traditionally male roles’ in the industry, respondents drew attention to the concentration of women in other occupations, such as in clerical jobs, in booking offices, commercial and marketing roles and HR roles.

Additionally, respondents provided evidence of not only role segregation according to gender but also hierarchical segregation, with the presence of ‘a glass ceiling’ and a lack of women in senior roles within their organisations. They suggested barriers exist which means that the further up the management chain you look the fewer women there are with examples of no women on management boards or in senior positions given. This lack of women in senior roles is problematic as respondents noted that women in senior roles, and more diverse roles, need to be more visible to make these positions seem more accessible to women, highlighting that they can progress and develop in their careers in the organisation and have a sense of ‘belonging’.

Overall, the DIAMOND Project found through its investigation that in most of the organisations represented by the respondent’s steps are being taken to improve gender balance and female employability at the point of recruitment and selection.

Despite the majority of respondents suggesting that recruitment practices and a cultural shift regarding views of women in the industry are positive and accepted, some pointed to resistance or best practice not always being upheld by everyone who makes hiring decisions. However, it was pointed out that although this cultural shift will take time to develop the impact of younger people, and their ideas of fairness, entering the industry could result in change.

In summary, it is clear that women have less favourable view of employment in the transport sector than men. There was some indication of less satisfaction with organisational culture such as inclusiveness of the organisation, gender balance in the sector and women's acceptance by male peers. Overall, women showed lower satisfaction with fairness and inclusivity of women in transport which must be properly acknowledged and addressed through education, specifically to consider the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment of women across the transport sector and to increase the participation of women as employees in the transport sector, including off-site professional positions - vehicle drivers, maintenance technicians and other currently less attractive positions for women. The main issues raised to achieve fairness and close the gender gap are presented below:

- a. **CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS** (for all employees):
 - ◆ Promotion and development opportunities;
 - ◆ Family friendly working conditions;
 - ◆ Training, work environment & culture;
 - ◆ Salary and conditions;
- b. **ACCESSIBILITY** (for all potential employees) :
 - ◆ Recruitment of women;
 - ◆ Specific training and career development for women;
 - ◆ Design;
- c. **SAFETY AND SECURITY** (for all frontline employees):
 - HR Policies on gender awareness and anti-bullying;

The proposed solutions to the main problems related to gender equality are inherent to good practices in the European Commission's final report (2019).

The deliverable D9.1 CSR protocols (DIAMOND Project, 2021b) focused on the measures to achieve a fair and gender inclusive working environment in the transport sector. The main topics or FCs level 3 associated to the 3 categories in which the recommendations are split into according to the target people in the employment sector are:

- **CAT 1: Topics that make women to love the transport sector**
 1. Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time
 2. Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave
- **CAT 2: Topics that make the sector to recruit more women**
 1. Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies
 2. Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions
 3. Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff
 4. Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies)
- **CAT 3: Topics with influence in the mid-long term for a more women represented transport sector**
 1. Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed
 2. Security staff available to intervene in case of need

3. Diversity training (re ethnicity)
4. Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment

3. New Curriculum Development Guidelines

In order to find answers to the women needs above, The DIAMOND Project has commissioned this Educational Curriculum Design Guidelines to support EU Universities and training centres offering graduate, postgraduate studies and in-company and occupational training to think creatively about how to design educational courses for gender inclusion based on a better understanding of women mobility needs, talent and motivations to address the discrimination in the transport sector. This curriculum design guideline is the ordered selection of experiences and needs developed from the DIAMOND Project for all learners to promote equity and social inclusion in the transport sector. The document sets out the objectives of the education system. In simple terms it prescribes what is to be achieved.

The concept of “curriculum” can be described as the teaching, learning, and assessment practices and materials available for a specific course or program. Thus, a curriculum is more than just a syllabus of content topics, it consists of a number of interrelated components and influences which are important to consider when designing a curriculum. This guide provides practical guidelines within a framework of principles of curriculum design that advocate for fairness and social equity in the transport sector. It is designed to assist programme leaders identify key issues in the transport sector to discuss with their teams; areas that require considerations.

During the stages of reviewing and redesigning the curriculum the team should discuss broad questions about the purpose of the programme and the role of the programme in engendering fairness and social equity in the transport systems. For example, how could the programme contribute to addressing the following concerns: How should technologies adapt to women needs? How should job characteristics be designed, and be disseminated to attract women? How should HR processes be carried out to avoid bias and discrimination against women? How can transport planners design transport services to meet women's requirements and expectations, and improve their access to transport and to jobs? The introduction of issues relating to fairness and social equity in the transport sector will offer the student/trainee the opportunities to explore their thoughts and feelings about the barriers and mobility and challenges of women and accessing job in the transport sector. Educational curriculum is one of the effective tools in supporting the society to acquire essential competencies to bridge the knowledge gap and address the gender disparities in the transport sector. Education is expected to be responsive to the challenges and needs of society. This mean systematic changes and reforms to national curriculum in response to national, regional, and global developmental challenges is essential in addressing societal challenges such as the mobility difficulties of women and closing the gender employment gap in the transport sector.

3.1 Models of the Curriculum

There are several models of curriculum, often divided into two simple models, i.e. competency-based and outcome-based curriculum with the chosen approach often lying at some point in between: a blend of central control and local autonomy. Discussions on curriculum centres around what is often termed an academic curriculum that focusses largely on specific subject knowledge and a more comprehensive curriculum that actively promotes the development of broader competencies, such as problem solving, initiative, and creativity. Opinions are often divided between the desire to achieve direct and measurable outcomes and the wider skills and competencies required by a modern, flexible knowledge-based economy.

A competency-based curriculum focuses on learners and trainees developing their understanding and competencies to apply knowledge in practical situations, rather than knowledge itself. A competency-based curriculum goes beyond the recall of information and focuses on competencies, such as communication, judgement, analysis and problem solving.

A blend of the competency-based and outcome-based curriculum is recommended in delivering the actionable knowledge developed by the DIAMOND project for a more inclusive and efficient transport systems. The guideline sets out the objectives for the education system. In simple terms it prescribes competencies to be achieved.

3.2 Content of the curriculum

This initial stage involves data mining and analytics, together with the use of elicitation to identify, design and evaluate specific measurements for fulfilling women's needs and expectations from the transport sector. To achieve this objective, the DIAMOND project investigated four selected transport sub-sectors (e.g., Public transport and infrastructure: Railways, Autonomous Vehicles technology, Vehicle (bike) sharing and Employment of women in the transport industry). Figure I illustrate the methodology used for the investigation and development of the actionable knowledge by the DIAMOND project. The purpose is this process was to understand women needs in the transport industry.

It is important to build an understanding on the knowledge gap to address through education to support gender inclusion in current and future transport systems from the perspective of women as transport users and as professionals in the sector.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the data collection and data analysis process.

The appreciation of the inequalities is key in the development of the content of the curriculum and helps in answering the following key questions:

- a) what competencies do graduates need in industry?
- b) what knowledge should be taught?

The questions about the competencies and knowledge to be taught was answered asking a number of gender experts, users of the transport systems and employee in the transport sector and presented the needs and challenges according to their personal viewpoint for curriculum considerations. The knowledge gathered in the DIAMOND project is fed into this stage of the Curriculum design guideline process for providing recommendations on the competencies and knowledge required to achieve fair gender inclusiveness in different scenarios and promoting female employment in the sector.

4. General guidelines for curriculum development

Curricula for programmes offered by higher education and training institutions (e.g. universities) is to ensure for future transport professionals acquire the required knowledge and competences to adequately address the challenges of women and inequalities in the transport sector. The process of developing and delivering the curriculum is continuous. Healthy education systems are characterised by constant change: the relentless quest for improvement and excellence. Much of this change is small scale: teachers striving to improve their lessons, schools trying to improve the learning experience, local level education authorities seeking ways to improve standards, governments adapting and refining policy. New ideas, guidelines, books and other resources constantly come into the education system to improve the delivery of the curriculum. This process of change is a response to changing knowledge, understanding and belief of what is working and what is not.

The quality of the outcome of university education is measured using graduates' success in their respective professions, this depends on different stakeholders who should be involved in the design, control and operation of this process.

4.1 Curriculum profile

In the context of the curriculum development, curriculum profile refers to the characteristics of the individual programme in question. Curriculum development seek to build qualifications that reflect a number of things including: their expertise; the scope of the programme and the needs of students, society and industry. Moreover, it is useful if curriculum development teams give detailed thought to the purposes and context of the qualifications. It is also beneficial for curriculum development teams to answer the following questions adapted from the UK Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) gender equality in case of successful completion. The curriculum profile should:

- be informative and include concise learning outcomes
- be inspiring with new ideas and research in the field
- show clear benefits for students, the transport industry and gender equality

What do we want our students to achieve?

This may include subject knowledge and understanding, a range of competences to develop, and transferable skills. Learning outcome statements can be developed by completing sentences like:

- This programme is distinctive because it develops...
- The most important values which inform this programme are...
- The academic content of this programme concentrates on...
- The most useful practical skills, techniques & capabilities developed are...
- Competency will be developed in...
- On completing the programme, we want students to know & understand...
- On completing the programme, we want students to be able to....

The design of curriculum profiles is premised on the fact that a learning process is more likely to deliver the defined learning outcomes if it is part of a properly designed programme implementing a coherent curriculum. This curriculum profile is to offer a concise overview of the curriculum, with a focus on the benefits for the attendees, the transport sector and

To be more precise, the most relevant FCs level 3 or factors for women as a homogeneous group are identified in Section 2.1 (UC-I, UC-II and UC-III) and Section 2.2 (UC-IV) and they will be topics that should be highlighted to be trained in the specific courses for people linked in some way with the transport system.

Training that should be included in the curriculum to increase the number of women as users in the transport system.

Training institutions should clearly indicate that they pay special attention on training the following topics:

For railways companies (UC-I):

1. Training about how to provide an adequate personal space;
2. Training about the most appropriate layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).
3. Ventilation and air-conditioning training.
4. Training about how to optimize the walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points
5. Training on how integrate the railways with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.
6. Training about the best location of complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety and how to manage it
7. Training regarding the visibility of the surrounding area of the station;
8. Training about the better number of service that should be available within the transport infrastructure
9. Training about how to increase the reliability of the service modes available
10. Training about how to integrate the railways with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing

As an example from the above list, highlighting institutions that they will help people to gain skills about the ventilation and air conditioning systems will attract people who wants to work in the railways field as it is a relevant factor that will help companies to increase the number of women using this mean of transport.

For autonomous vehicles (UC-II):

1. Training to reduce drivers' perception of boredom
2. Training to increase drivers' perception of joy
3. Training on the perception of the degree of interaction between passengers
4. Training on how to show drivers that AVs reduce the ecological impact
5. Training on controlling speed in the AVs

6. Training about how to drive when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment
7. Training to be able to increase the trust in technology in the case of bad weather
8. Training about the vehicle behaviour under sportive driving
9. Training about optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour
10. Training about how the public health is perceived when driving without steering wheel

For bike sharing services (UC-III):

1. Training about making public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
2. Training about cycling rain Poncho
3. Training about how to avoid hilly terrains in the development of cycle networks where possible.
4. Training about weather cycle-friendly infrastructures
5. Training about how to make attractive changing facilities
6. Training about introducing bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.
7. Training about how to build safe cycle routes for cycling with children
8. Training about introducing end-of-trip cycling facilities
9. Training about making better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
10. Training about how lower the traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes

Training that should be included to make women love working in the transport sector.

Companies and training institutions should clearly indicate that they pay special attention on training the following topics:

1. Training how to give the best opportunity to change shifts or to reduce those with small children their working time
2. Training about how to include in the companies family friendly policies such as maternity and paternity leave

Providing training to better plan the traffic and fleets will allow people a more flexible working and also working from home.

Training that should be included to increase the fairness in the employment of the transport sector in a mid-long term.

Companies and training institutions should clearly indicate that they pay special attention on training the following topics:

1. Training about how to widely advertise the employment opportunities how to achieve that all applications are welcomed
2. Training on how to introduced available security staff to intervene in case of need
3. Training to be tolerant with all people (diversity training and ethnicity)

4. Training about applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment

The core of each profile comprises the learning outcomes from completion: the knowledge, skills and competences which a programme delivers to shape the skills and competences of transport professionals.

4.2 Define outcomes

The output of the education or training in gender equality in the transport sector should provide the student or transport professional with the knowledge and competences relevant to addressing the inequality in the transport industry regarding women transportation needs, recruitment and retention in the sector. The main stakeholders here are university professors, gender experts, women groups, representatives from the transport industry, industrial and professional associations, accreditation bodies, government, and, the students or trainees. A valuable input for defining the outcomes of this curricula are the finding of the DIAMOND project

To develop the competences to assess gender inequalities in the transport sector (women transportation and employment needs) to design solutions

- Understanding women mobility challenges and needs
- Understanding women employment challenges and needs
- Understanding the inequalities in the transport sector
- Design solutions to eliminate the inequalities

5. Recommendations for designing new curricula

The concerns of gender inequality and discrimination against Women underscores the role of education in promoting equality of men and women to eliminate discrimination against women to ensure to their equal rights with men. As a result, curriculum design guidelines for future transport professionals and reflecting educational novel contents on:

- how technologies should adapt to women needs,
- how job characteristics should be designed and be disseminated to attract women
- how HR processes should be carried out to avoid bias and discrimination, and
- how transport planners should design transport services to meet women's mobility needs

The guidelines need to be designed and targeted at future professionals aiming at careers within the transport system, as well as current professionals, from trainers, policy makers, researchers, external consultants, transport planners, staff managers, HR managers, designers, ICT developers, on-site and off-site workers. EU Universities and training centres offering graduate, postgraduate studies and in-company and occupational training should develop a new curriculum to meet the needs of traditional full-time learners as well as non-traditional learners such as part-time learners and mature students.

5.1 Curriculum Structure

In general, no curriculum can prepare students for activities at expert level in all skill profiles. However, a well-designed, cohesive and connected curriculum delivered in semesters should be able to equip the transport professional with the requisite knowledge and competences to address gender inequalities in the transport sector. It is recommended that the curriculum should consist of hierarchically organised modules based on:

- a) sets of core modules and
- b) sets of area-specific core modules;

In the area of technical knowledge:

- a) the core modules should consist of fundamental and basic gender studies. In particular, it should provide the competences and skills enable the trainees and students become aware of the gender difference and inequality between men and women.
- b) the area-specific core modules represent industry specific areas such as public transport infrastructure design and services, vehicle sharing services, employment in the rail, maritime or aviation sector.

Largely, they should be integrated into the teaching of technical subjects. Where additional modules are necessary, they should follow the same structure as the technical knowledge area.

5.2 Clustering of skills profiles

Educational or training curriculum should show how to handle gender needs in transport planning, in service offerings, and how to tackle job opportunities fairly. The new level of curriculum for future transport professionals sets out the content and specific details of what competencies students and trainees should develop and what the learning outcomes should result at each stage/year/ of schooling.

The syllabi and desired competencies are presented below and organised under two categories: transport infrastructure and service delivery, and Employment in the transport industry. The syllabus for each category gives sufficient details for the curriculum design team to produce appropriate content for each study group.

a) *Transport infrastructure and service delivery*

The expected learning outcome for this subject area is a better understanding of the mobility challenges of women and the competencies to develop recommendations to improve transport infrastructure and services in the following areas:

- Accessibility
 - Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points
 - Reliability of the service modes available
 - Level of service at the public transport access point
 - Number of service available within the transport infrastructure
 - Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, alternative shared mobility service,
 - Provision of safety equipment such as helmets, hi-vis vest, rain ponchos for bike-sharing services
 - Provision of bike-sharing services in low-income neighbourhoods
 - Provision of attractive changing facilities by organisations for cyclists
- Safety and security
 - Visibility of the surrounding area of the station
 - Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety
 - Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers
 - Offering adequate personal space
 - Improved ventilation and air-conditioning
 - Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)
 - Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes for cyclists
- Social constraints
 - Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
 - Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
 - Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
 - Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.
 - Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.

- Weather and Topography
 - Provision of all-weather cycle-friendly infrastructure

To be more precise and according to the identified FCs level 3, the curricula for UC-I should include:

1. Specific knowledge on how to provide an adequate personal space;
2. Specific knowledge on the most appropriate layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).
3. Specific knowledge on ventilation and air-conditioning systems.
4. Specific knowledge on how to optimize the walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points
5. Specific knowledge on how integrate the railways with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.
6. Specific knowledge on the best location of complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety and how to manage it
7. Specific knowledge on the visibility of the surrounding area of the station;
8. Specific knowledge on the better number of service that should be available within the transport infrastructure
9. Specific knowledge on how to increase the reliability of the service modes available
10. Specific knowledge on how to integrate the railways with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing

As an example, from the above list, highlighting people that they have skills about the ventilation and air conditioning systems will help them to work in the railways systems companies as it was identified as a barrier that will increase the number of women using the railways.

Regarding UCIII, the identified FCs level 3, the curricula should include:

1. Specific knowledge on making public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
2. Specific knowledge on cycling rain Poncho
3. Specific knowledge on how to avoid hilly terrains in the development of cycle networks where possible.
4. Specific knowledge on making weather cycle-friendly infrastructures
5. Specific knowledge on how to make attractive changing facilities
6. Specific knowledge on how to introduce bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.
7. Specific knowledge on how to build safe cycle routes for cycling with children
8. Specific knowledge on how to introduce end-of-trip cycling facilities
9. Specific knowledge on how to make better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
10. Specific knowledge on how lower the traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes

b) *Autonomous vehicle Technology*

The expected learning outcome also include a better understanding of the design and functionality of autonomous vehicles to meet women mobility needs, and the knowledge and competencies to develop recommendations to improve the design of autonomous vehicles in the following areas to meet women needs:

- Safety and security
 - Trust in technology in the case of bad weather
 - Human Machine Interface (warning and communication system);
 - Safe ergonomics.
 - Controlling speed

- Accessibility
 - Vehicle shape (getting in and out of the car);
 - Vehicle shape (seating);
 - Vehicle shape (shopping/suitcases);
 - Human Machine Interface (ergonomics);
 -
 - Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers
 - Performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment
 - Perception of public health when driving without steering wheel
 - Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour

To be precise and according to the identified FCs level 3, the curricula for this UC-II should include:

1. Specific knowledge on how to reduce drivers' perception of boredom
2. Specific knowledge on how to increase drivers' perception of joy
3. Specific knowledge on how to deal with the perception of the degree of interaction between passengers
4. Specific knowledge on how to show drivers that AVs reduce the ecological impact
5. Specific knowledge on how to control the speed in the AVs
6. Specific knowledge on how to drive when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment
7. Specific knowledge on how to be able to increase the trust in technology in the case of bad weather
8. Specific knowledge on vehicle behaviour under sportive driving
9. Specific knowledge on how to optimise the well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour
10. Specific knowledge on how the public health is perceived when driving without steering wheel

c) *Promoting women employment in the transport industry*

- How to provide flexible working contracts (How to give women with children the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time)

- How to create family friendly working conditions for different categories of workers (e.g. professions that require prolonged absence from home)
- Recruitment policy (How to advertise employment opportunities to attract more women)
- Workplace security enhancement (How to make security staff available to intervene in case of need and additional safety process for night staff and those working alone)
- Policy and education of sexual harassment (Zero tolerance policy on sexual harassment)
- Diversity training in general and specifically for ethnicity
- HR policies to ensure gender equality in the workplace
- Gender pay gap (gender pay equality for equivalent positions)
- Fairness and equity in the recruitment and promotion processes (Equal employment policies: organisation policies to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements)

According to the identified FCs level 3, the curricula to increase the recruitment of women in UC-IV should include:

1. Specific knowledge on how to integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies
2. Specific knowledge on how to ensure gender pay equality for equivalent positions
3. Specific knowledge on how to ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff
4. Specific knowledge on making equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies)

The expected outcome of the guidelines will be an increased readiness of transport systems and educational courses for gender inclusion based on a better understanding of women mobility needs, talents and motivations in job opportunities.

Programme teams should ensure that there is clarity, cohesion and connections in the programme between modules that are delivered in semesters. Staff and students should experience the curriculum as a whole, at the programme level, rather than as a collection of individual modules. During the early stages of reviewing and redesigning the curriculum the team should discuss broad questions about the purpose of the programme.

6. Conclusion

It is hoped that the successful implementation of these guidelines will be of mutual benefit to women and the transport industry, enhancing and strengthening gender equality and ensuring fairness and equity in the transport sector. It will reduce if not eliminate all forms of discriminations in the sector and encourage more women to seek job opportunities in the sector as well as address the mobility challenges of women in public transportation, vehicle sharing services and the adoption of autonomous vehicles.

7. Resources

Resource	Reference
GEAR Action Toolbox	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/action-toolbox
Gender Toolkit Transport	Link
HER CITY	Link
LIBRA Recruitment Handbook	Corrales, C., Herzig, M., Lloyd, C., Meixner, B., & Steiner, M. (2017). <i>LIBRA Recruitment HANDBOOK</i> . www.eu-libra.eu
Pedestrian First	https://pedestriansfirst.itdp.org/
Sustainable Urban Mobility Indicators-benchmarking tool	Link
Women in Transport –EN Platform	Link

References

- Adams, J., Greig, M., McQuaid, R. (2000) 'Mismatch unemployment and local labour-market efficiency: the role of employer and vacancy characteristics', *Environment and Planning A* (32) pp 1841 -1856 accessed [here](#)
- AQU Catalunya. (2019). *General framework for Incorporating the gender perspective in higher education teaching* (pp. 1–69).
- Basarić, A., Vujičić, A., Mitrović, J., Bogdanović, V., Nenad Saulić, N. (2016) 'Gender and Age Differences in the Travel Behaviour – A Novi Sad Case Study', *Transportation Research Procedia* (14) pp4324-4333 accessed [here](#)
- Caulfield, B., O'Mahony, M., Brazil, W., & Weldon, P. (2017) Examining usage patterns of a bike-sharing scheme in a medium sized city. *Transportation research part A: policy and practice*, vol. 100, pp. 152-161.
- Cascetta, E. (2013) *Transportation systems engineering: theory and methods*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Bowling, B. (2007) Fair and Effective Policing Methods: Towards 'Good Enough' Policing, *Journal of Scandinavian Studies in Criminology and Crime Prevention*, 8:sup1, 17-32, DOI: 10.1080/14043850701695023
- Corral, A. and Isusi, I. (2007) Innovative gender equality measures in the transport industry *European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions* accessed [here](#)
- DIAMOND project, (2020). Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition.
- French, E. and Strachan, G. (2008) 'Evaluating equal employment opportunity and its impact on the increased participation of men and women in the transport industry', *Transportation Research Part A*, 43, pp. 78-89 accessed [here](#)
- Geurs, K.T., Boon, W. and Van Wee, B. (2009) 'Social Impacts of Transport: Literature Review and the State of the Practice of Transport Appraisal in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom', *Transport Reviews*, 29, 1, 69–90.
- Giannelos, I., Smit, G., Lakamp, R., Gonzalez Martinez, A., Dorantes, L., Doll, C., Tanis, J., Vroonhof, P. and Perciaccante, F. (2008) *Business case to increase female employment in Transport* accessed [here](#)
- Guenther, E. Humbert, A and Kelan. E. (2018) 'Gender Vs. Sex', *Oxford Research Encyclopaedia Business and Management* accessed [here](#)
- Hail, Y. and McQuaid, R. (2021). 'The concept of fairness in relation to women transport users', *Sustainability*, 13, 5, 2919. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052919> accessed [here](#)
- Hanson, S. (2010) Gender and mobility: 'New approaches for informing sustainability', in *Gender Place and Culture*, 1, pp. 5-23
- Houston, D and Tilley, S (2016) 'The gender turnaround: Young women now travelling more than young men', *Journal of Transport Geography*, 54, pp. 349-358 accessed [here](#)
- Kaplan, S., Manca, F., Nielsen, T. A. S., and Prato, G. (2015) Intentions to use bike-sharing for holiday cycling: An application of the Theory of Planned Behavior. *Tourism Management*, vol 47, pp. 34-46.
- Koester, D. (2015). *DLP Concept Brief 04: Gender & Power*. 1–7. <http://publications.dlprog.org/Gender&Power.pdf>
- Lee, R., Sener, N. and Jones, N. (2017) 'Understanding the role of equity in active transportation planning in the United States', *Transport Review* 37 (20) pp211-226 accessed [here](#)
- Levy, K. (2013) 'Travel choice reframed: "deep distribution" and gender in urban transport', *Environment and Urbanization*, 25(1), pp47–63 accessed [here](#)

- Lucas, K., van Wee, B., & Maat, K. (2015). 'A method to evaluate equitable accessibility: Combining ethical theories and accessibility-based approaches', *Transportation*, 1–18. doi:10.1007/s11116-015-9585-2
- Madariaga, I. (2013) 'From Women in Transport to Gender in Transport: Challenging Conceptual Frameworks for Improved Policy Making', *Journal of International Affairs* 67 (1)
- Martens K. (2012) 'Justice in transport as justice in accessibility: applying Walzer's 'Spheres of Justice' to the transport sector', *Transportation* (39) pp pages1035–1053 accessed [here](#)
- Meyer, M. D. (2016) *Transportation planning handbook*. John Wiley & Sons
- McIntosh, B., McQuaid, R., Munro, A., and Dabir-Alai, P. (2012) 'Motherhood and its impact on career progression – the case of Scottish nurses 2000-2008', *Gender in Management*, 27, 5, 346-364.
- McQuaid, R. and Chen, T. (2012) 'Commuting times – the role of gender, children and part time work', *Research in Transportation Economics*, 34, 66-73 accessed [here](#)
- The Gender Issue: Beyond Exclusion* (FALL/WINTER 2013), pp. 43-65
- United Nations. (1996). *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women*.
- Pereira, R.H.M., Schwanen, T. and Banister, D. (2017) 'Distributive justice and equity in transportation', *Transport Reviews*, 37(2), 170-191.
- Scott, J. (2018) *The Persistence of Gender Inequality How politics constructs gender, and gender constructs politics* accessed [here](#)
- Social Exclusion Unit (2003) *Making the Connections: Final Report on Transport and Social Exclusion*. London: ODPM.
- Wright, T. (2014) 'Gender, sexuality and male-dominated work: the intersection of long-hours working and domestic life', *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(6) pp. 985–1002 accessed [here](#)
- Yerkes, M. A., Martin, B., Baxter, J., & Rose, J. (2017). An unsettled bargain? Mothers' perceptions of justice and fairness in paid work. *Journal of Sociology*, 53(2), 476–491. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1440783317696361>

